

SECURITY KNOWLEDGE REQUIRED TO IMPROVE EMPLOYEE SECURITY BEHAVIOR IN INFORMATION SECURITY CULTURE

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Abstract: *There are many security risks to the organizations' information assets; nonetheless, among the major threats to achieve a secure information environment are the actions and behavior of the employees when handling information. Insiders, intentionally or unintentionally, can cause serious risks, despite investments usually made on security control measures and other security related products. Insecure human behavior with respect to information security cannot entirely be solved by technical and procedural controls alone. Recently, the development of effective information security culture in organizations is increasingly considered as a way to embed appropriate security practices, and to address the human factor in information security. Past research works on this area indicate that there is a positive relationship between levels of knowledge and how employees behave. The level of knowledge significantly affects information security behavior and should be considered as a critical factor in the effectiveness of information security culture and in any further work that is carried out on information security culture. Therefore, in this paper we have identified the security knowledge required to improve employee behavior in information security culture namely; knowledge of security threat, knowledge of organization information security strategy, knowledge of security technology, knowledge of legislation, regulation and national culture, knowledge of security responsibility and knowledge of security risk. These security knowledge needs to be included as topics in security training and awareness programs conducted by organizations for their employees so that an effective information security culture within the organization can be achieved.*

Keywords: *Information Security, Information Security Culture, Human Behavior and Security knowledge.*

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the top highlighted issues in organizational culture is information security culture. It is described as a sub-category of the organizational culture that encompasses day-to-day processes, activities, guidelines and practices among organizational employees that assist them in protecting the information assets within the organization and minimize the risks facing such assets [1].

Past literature (e.g., [2]–[5]) claimed that information security culture has to be viewed as a goal to be accomplished in order to develop a culture that covers the entire activities and guidelines required for information security to be part of the daily activities of every organizational employee. Dhillon [6] defines information security culture as “The collection of human attributes such as behaviors, attitudes, and values that facilitate the protection of all the information in the organization”. Veiga & Eloff [7] define information security culture as “The attitudes, assumptions, beliefs, values and knowledge that employees use to interact with the organization’s systems and procedures at any point in time. The interaction results in acceptable or unacceptable behavior evident in the artifacts and creations that become part of the way things are done in the organization to protect its information assets”. Furthermore, Mahfuth et al. [8] define information security culture as the integration process of beliefs, perceptions, attitudes, values, assumptions and knowledge that guiding, directing and managing employees’ security behavior to establish acceptable behavior when interacting with the organization’s information assets. Stated differently, it is crucial for the organization and employees to collaborate to facilitate a suitable environment for information security culture to be adopted throughout the organization.

Establishing effective information security culture in organizations impacts employees’ perceptions, values, assumptions, knowledge and behavior in a way that can guard against many information security threats posed by insiders. It can lead an employee to act as a

“human firewall” that can safeguard organizational information assets. Furthermore, Naser et al. [9] define the different dimensions of Information Security Culture found in the Information Security Policy (ISP) compliance behavior literature. An analysis of literature review conducted by [10], [11],[12] & [13] indicated there is a positive relationship between levels of knowledge and how employees behave. The level of knowledge significantly affects information security behavior and should be considered as a critical factor in the effectiveness of information security culture

This paper adopted the systematic literature review (SLR) approach to identify the security knowledge required to improve the employees’ behavior when handling organizations information assets. The knowledge needs to be incorporated into organizations and should be instilled as a daily practice to influence the employee behavior in the organizations. Furthermore, it helps to find the best practice for building an information security culture within organizations. In addition, the SLR identified different methodologies and empirical studies that aimed at exploring the nature of information security culture. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: In section 2, the research method adopted to conduct the SLR is described. Then in section 3 the definitions of security knowledge are presented, followed by an overview of the security knowledge required to improve employee behavior in section 4. This is followed by a discussion and the conclusion in section 5.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

In this paper, the relevant literature on security knowledge, employee security behavior and information security culture was collected to be reviewed and analyzed systematically through using the so-called qualitative content analysis. This type of analysis utilizes a subjective interpretation of the text content by means of using a systematic classification process of coding to identify certain themes or patterns in that

text. In order to carry out the search process the researcher focused on the content of electronic databases such as Springer, Google Scholar, ACM and IEEE Electronic Library. A qualitative content analysis was used to identify and classify the papers accordingly.

3. SECURITY KNOWLEDGE DEFINITION

In the organizations, it has become a must to provide security knowledge to employees can safeguard information assets, affect human behavior and decrease security incidents. Employees should possess sufficient security knowledge to safeguard organization assets from security threats and vulnerabilities. Security knowledge has been defined in different ways by experts in the area. Some of the more common definitions are provided in the next paragraphs.

According to [1], in information security context, basic security knowledge is about members in the organization who are able to perform, learn and teach security tasks with respect to inspection, protection, detection, reaction, and reflection procedures on security matters. Knowledge has to be integrated in the processes of the organization, its practices, activities, routines and norms, and each employee has to be responsible for it in their day-to-day activities rather than just being left in documents and reports.

Despite the derivation of knowledge from information, it can also become information as explained by Alavi & Leidner [14]. They indicated that information is transformed into knowledge after processing in the mind of the individual, and after it is articulated and presented in text, words, graphics and other symbolic forms. This shows that knowledge can transform into information after it is shared in documents, books, policies, procedures, computers or other types of repositories. It reverts back to knowledge if it is relayed to other individuals [15]. It is impossible for organizations to ensure the integrity, confidentiality and availability of

information assets without the consideration of employee behavior in order to safeguard organization assets. The provision of security knowledge to employees can work towards promoting successful implementation of information systems in the organization. Implementation of security knowledge will assist in inculcating the required security knowledge between the organization employees and in promoting understanding among employees of their roles and responsibilities in safeguarding information assets. This knowledge can be instilled through education, training, and awareness initiatives [5]. Security knowledge has to be developed in day-to-day activities supporting the business activities as part of the culture of the organization. In other words, information security culture should become a natural practice in day-to-day employee activities. Cultivating each employee's security knowledge plays a crucial role in bringing about their desired behavior. It is crucial that employees understand and act towards securing the information assets of the organization [16].

In relation to the above, there are two dimensions to the human factor of information security and they are knowledge and behavior, and the two dimensions are interconnected [17]. In fact, owing to the interdependence between the dimensions, it becomes impossible to ignore the effect of lack of information security related knowledge on organizational sub-culture of information security. Hence, it is important for security knowledge to be integrated into the day-to-day activities of every employee.

4. SECURITY KNOWLEDGE REQUIRED TO IMPROVE EMPLOYEE BEHAVIOR

The related studies concerning security knowledge was gathered for systematic review and analysis using qualitative content analysis. Such analysis uses a subjective interpretation of the text content using a systematic process of classification that codes and identifies themes/patterns within the text.

In the following subsections, the security knowledge required to influence the employee behavior are resented. These security knowledge needed to be provided to employees in order to enhance their behavior in their interaction with information assets of the organization in order to lessen the risks towards such assets.

4.1 Knowledge of Security Threat

In the world of technology, the threats are innumerable and are of different types and goals, like vandalism, thievery or extortion. There are many forms of cyber-threats, with some common ones taking the forms of, viruses-a set of computer programs that can disturb or slow down the performance of the computer or prevent normal functioning of computer systems or malware – malicious software/program that can harm information systems such as viruses, spyware, trojan horses or worms. Threat has a negative consequences such as loss of data, loss of money and blocking access to information [13]. These threats are often introduced to the organizations via email attachments or programs downloaded from the Internet. It can also come in the form of Spam: an unsolicited e-mail or undesirable email, spyware: monitoring and spy software, denial of services attacks to make computer resources unavailable to the users, social engineering to obtain a confidential information via interaction or communication with insiders, or phishing to perform a malicious action. The main objectives of these threats may be to steal, monitor, change or expose confidential data or assets related to the users.

Employees inside the organization pose direct or indirect threats to the organizations, with the information assets within vulnerable to cyber-attacks that are more often than not, detrimental to the organizational performance. Thus, the inculcation of security knowledge culture among employees will contribute towards lessening the threats within the organization and protecting its information assets. Organizational employees always have to be aware of threats and to achieve this, security

knowledge regarding security threats has to be instilled in them. The organization should provide security knowledge in terms of threats to employees to direct and manage their behavior in their interaction with its assets.

4.2 Knowledge of Organization Information Security Strategy

The organization information security strategy describes the suitable implementation of various information security strategies such as plans of actions, policies, objectives, best practices, standards, guidelines and priorities that guide employees to accomplish goals to safeguard information assets.

Studies in literature have examined the relationship between information security culture and security policies (e.g., [5], [18], [19]. More specifically,[7] stated that information security policies is an important component of information security culture, while [20] suggested that security policy development needs to be supported by the security culture of the organization.

Added to the above, [21] argued the primary aim of a policy is to drive the decisions, actions and behaviors of employees relating to their interaction with the information assets. Such policy explains employees' acceptable behavior; for example, the information security policy mandates that laptop must be physically secured at all times. The policy statement aims to direct employee behavior towards the protection of physical assets and data saved in the laptop – it aims to influence the behavior of the employee when using the laptop to ensure its safety. The absence of such statement and its enforcement could lead to employees being careless of their laptop's security. In other words, lack of information security component to direct and influence employee behavior could lead to employees leaving information assets at risk. The negative consequences could lead to an unacceptable culture of neglect.

Employees would comply with information security policies and practices if they understand the importance of information security in protecting the valuable assets of the organization against unauthorized and intentional misuse by individuals that violate hardware, software, data and computer services [22]. This can be done via management support, and the provision of information security programs and information security guidelines that are clear. The level of user awareness can be maximized if the whole organization practices the recommended information security, and in turn, this brings about successful implementation of information system security within the organization.

In a similar line of study, Siponen et al. (2007) related that in case employees are privy to the information security policy, they are more likely to comply with it. Employees primarily focus on their tasks and jobs and may not be aware of the new policy (e.g., new password requirements) but an effective information security culture ensures that they are made aware of it to protect their computers and sensitive information against threats, this way adherence becomes a norm.

In organization, the management must focus on how each statement of the organization's policies, guidelines and strategies has to be positively stated to influence human behavior and to uphold information security culture. The objective has to be geared towards instilling information security behavior that protects information assets based on the information security policies, strategies, guidelines and best practices of the organization. This type of behavior could entail reporting security incidents, compliance with clear desk policy, or secured disposal of confidential documents.

Providing security knowledge about organization information security strategy directs employees' behavior to safeguard information assets, facilitate oversight and determine who has control access. This necessitates the employees' obtaining knowledge on the policy and its positive

outcomes directed towards protecting assets as a result of complying with the policy. The objective of policy is to influence and to improve the employees' behavior to ensure the protection of information assets.

4.3 Knowledge of Security Technology

In this paper, knowledge of security technology is knowledge concerning hardware, software, services, appliances and applications employed by the organization for the protection of information assets [24]. Disseminating knowledge concerning security technology has a key role in forming information security culture and in influencing and enhancing employees' behavior towards protecting the organization from within. Stated clearly, creating and maintaining an effective information security culture will facilitate the use of various security technology measures. For instance, the antivirus software would be useless to the organization without its regular update. This holds true for the other security technologies deployed by the company when inappropriately utilized by employees. Developing knowledge of security technology would thus contribute to urging employees' behavior towards protecting the organizational assets by using available security technology correctly.

Majority of organizations use different technology control for the protection of information security and for the prevention of threats and security attacks; for instance, the use of firewall, antivirus software, access management systems, these are aimed to safeguard the organization from threats and attacks and to support its security strategy. Nevertheless, the lack of sufficient knowledge of employees on policy usage of technology may lead to ineffective use of them and may do more harm than good to the organization. Therefore, providing security knowledge about security technology is a vital to influence the employee behavior inside the organization.

4.4 Knowledge of Legislation, Regulation and National Culture

The organization's external environment and national culture significantly impact its information security culture. According to [25], organizations develop their information security assumption on the basis of their social values reflecting the environment. Stated clearly, the legislation, regulation, and national culture of the environment within which the organization is run have to be considered when designing the organization's structure, its information security culture, and security of information assets (Hogail, 2015) [26].

Several studies have been dedicated to this topic and they focused on external factors that influence the information security culture, including national and cultural factors (e.g., [27]–[29]). Similarly, Dojkovski et al. [30] highlighted national and ethical culture as well as government legislation as an external factors that have the potential to influence information security culture.

Further, the primary factors provided in [29] study are corporate governance, legal and regulatory environment and corporate citizens. The author also indicated that security culture is influenced by organizational culture that is affected by national culture. The study revealed that corporate governance, legal and regulatory environment and corporate citizens all influence an organization's information security culture.

In this regard, several studies in literature evidenced the significant impact of national culture on the implementation of information security culture and the employees' behavior [27], [28], [31], [32]. Moreover, national culture determines the values and beliefs of the members of the organization because it naturally influences the viewpoints of the members, their duties and their interaction – in sum; it defines acceptable and not-acceptable behavior in the organization. This indicates that when information security culture is designed, national culture has to be taken into consideration due to its influence on human behavior. Also, employees should be knowledgeable on legislation, regulation

and national culture when it comes to privacy issues and security information laws, as well as intellectual property.

Moving on to legislation, Al Hogail [27] argued that an effective information security culture within an organization can be ensured by taking legislation into account in that government regulations concerning information security has to be applied (e.g., copyrights). It is crucial to inform employees of relevant government information security linked to legislation. On the above studies, it is clear that providing these knowledge to employee help to influence their behavior to protect the organization information assets.

4.5 Knowledge of Security Responsibility

The employees working for the organization is deemed to form the core of its information security culture on account of their important role in protecting information in the information security process [17], [33], [34]. Information security culture primarily aims to facilitate employees' behavior to work towards the security of information assets, from the top management level to the most menial worker [35]. One of its main goals is to establish that information security is the responsibility of every employee, in that the knowledge of security responsibility culture has to be inculcated in each employee in order to protect the organization from within. Al Hogail in [26] stressed that information security culture has to consider every human factor to enhance user security behavior. In reality, majority of the employees think that the security of information falls on the IT department's responsibility [36], when in fact, employees should be aware of their security related roles and responsibilities and their security behavior (ISO/IEC27001:2013). The concept of knowledge of security responsibility should be established among all employees to have a positive impact on their behavior. The responsibility of top management in this case is to develop security measures for the data protection, to commit towards data protection and information security to promote the

desired behavior of employees. The management should also have as strategies to improve information security in the organization [27].

Knowledge of security responsibility has to be disseminated among employees through training and awareness in order to achieve the desired employees' behavior and to improve information security culture [37], [38]. Employees have to be educated of their security related roles and responsibilities and trained to behave in a secure manner. They should know how to effectively use information security applications and procedures and what is expected from in their interaction with information assets. They should also know what to do when they detect a security breach, how to disclose threats and risks that can potentially harm information assets. In sum, they should know what to protect, why it needs protection and how they be a part of the protection [39].

Conversely, the employees should be made accountable for their actions, these actions should be taken against employees who fail to comply with information security requirements. In relation to this, top management should establish clear policies and formal reward and punitive processes for effective information security culture. Security responsibility culture should be promoted within the organization through reward and deterrence processes and security oversight. There are evidence that have shown that rewarding desirable behavior and punishing undesirable ones would maximize the adherence of employees to information security needs [2], [7].

4.6 Knowledge of Security Risk

Similar to the previous types of knowledge, this is equally important to drive human behavior in their interaction with the organization's information assets and to understand the risks present in the environment of the information assets. In 2018, a security violation survey by PWC (Price Waterhouse Coopers) revealed that 28% of major organizations reported security breaches from within, 57% of small

organizations experienced insiders related security violation, and 36% of the breaches stemmed from unintentional human behavior (Information Security Breaches Survey, 2018) (Correct the referencing method). For the establishment of an effective information security culture in the organization, focus should be placed on risks linked with unmanaged behavior. It is crucial to educate employees and alert them on the risks and dangers stemming from the environment that surrounds information assets and the risks that may occur when employees are behaving insecurely within the organization [27].

Knowledge of security risk aims to promote employees' awareness of security risks and their responsibilities towards security that drive them towards acting in a secure way [7] & [40]. Additionally, the knowledge can assist employees to know, understand and adopt the required precautions and ensure that they possess the required skills for appropriate actions [41], and for the pursuant of secured behavior.

The careless and ignorant actions of the employees could lead to information security risks involuntarily; for example, if an employee retrieves spam email, opens email attachment with virus, or ignore information security policy on external drive use [30]. Moreover, the negligence of employees could leave the network to risk from malware, virus, worms and Trojans from infiltrating and infecting the whole system. This is also exemplified by employees using their personal devices without the right security protocols, in which case, the risks of exposing the network to security threats and attacks are increased. Authors in [42] stated that many employees carry mobile devices containing sensitive work related information outside their workplace, which could expose sensitive data to the risk of being leaked or stolen. Other behaviors that expose employees and data to security risks include downloading suspicious software, browsing through unsafe websites, sharing passwords, or leaving written passwords at open places in the office such as writing password on a post-it note and pasting it on the monitor.

Inculcating knowledge of security risk to employees will contribute towards safeguarding them, the organization and the information assets of the organization. It will also make them aware of the potential risks, which in turn, would affect their behavior and actions taken in conducting their work.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The objective of this paper was help to identify the security knowledge required to influence the employee behavior. These security knowledge needs to be incorporated into organizations and to find instances of best practice for the establishment of an information security culture within organizations.

A thorough review of literature revealed a relationship between employee knowledge and behavior. The employees' behavior have to be managed through knowledge to shape their assumptions and attitudes. Hence, this study presents how security knowledge enhances employee behavior in interacting with the information assets of the organization. These knowledge's need to be incorporated into organizations and should be instilled as a daily practice to influence the employee behavior in the organizations. Furthermore, it helps to find instances of best practice for building an information security culture within organizations.

Furthermore, employee training and awareness about these security knowledge are important in achieving their desired behavior and enhancing information security culture. It is hoped that the review provided in this paper will assist researchers who are interested in investigating this field further. As a future work, we will investigate the impact of these security knowledge constructs to employee behavior within organization.

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